

**ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING
AMONG ANTENATAL WOMEN VISITING PRIMARY HEALTH CARE
CENTRES IN RIVERS STATE**

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Abstract

Attitude towards cervical cancer screening is essential determinant for its acceptance and practice among women. This research examined the attitude towards cervical cancer screening among antenatal women visiting primary health care centres in Rivers State. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study consists of all the five hundred and fifty-five thousand, six hundred and fifty-one (555,651) women attending antenatal clinics in Rivers State. Sample size of 798 was determined using Taro Yamane formula. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select the sample. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.78. The completed copies of the questionnaire were retrieved, coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The descriptive statistics of percentage, frequency count and mean was used for demographic characteristics of the participants and research questions. While inferential statistics of chi-square set at 0.05 alpha level was used to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study showed that majority of the respondents had positive attitude towards cervical cancer. The result shows that there was no significant relationship between socio-demographic factors such as age ($p>0.05$), education ($p>0.05$), religion ($p>0.05$) and attitude towards cervical cancer screening. It was concluded that the antenatal women visiting primary health care centres in Rivers State has positive attitude towards cervical cancer screening. It was recommended that, the Ministry of Health should make effort to promote cervical cancer screening among women by establishing well-organized cervical cancer screening programme primary health care services.

Keywords: knowledge, cervical cancer screening, primary health care centre, ante-natal women